

Paper 11

A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY ON THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM FOR THE SOCIAL CHANGE

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Abstract:

The present article studies the importance of education in the personal, social and economic development of the nation. Education empowers our mind that will be able to conceive good thoughts and ideas. It also enables the students to do the analysis while making life decision. Unfortunately, schools and college teachers is only behind completing the syllabus for the year and the results of the examination. Today the result is excessively focused on memorization. Let's understand the essence and the purpose of education as articulated by the National Policy of Education,1986. The initiatives should be brought up by the teachers which helps in instilling the values and a greater sense for the purpose to prepare the future generations for the effective social makers. The education provided in schools and colleges and the efficient need for the society's growth should go hand in hand. Education must promote knowledge and integration among the people by broadening the visions of students and nationalism in the students.If we accept that, the education should influence on shaping society, then it is clear that we must focus on the real goals of education.

Keywords: Teaching, Educational system, Transformative learning, Development of personnel, Economic growth

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is the process of facilitating learning or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, value, belief and habits. Education empowers minds that will be able to conceive good thoughts and ideas. It is important to people of all the ages and it has no limit. It also enables the student to do the analysis while making life decision. Education can help the society in personal and National level. It has been shown to increase economic growth and stability. One of the most important benefits of education is how it improves personal lives and help societies to run smoothly. Education promotes fulfilling, fuller lifestyle.

When we look back 70's and 80's, many people survived without education. But in current situation, much more competition raised among students. At the same time, students have lot of facilities for their higher studies. Since we have all facilities and technologies, students can study hard and compete with their level of a student.

Education plays a vital role in social change but the present Educational Policies doesn't give the exposure to social change. It must assist in molding the attitude of people but also in creating a desire for change by providing right knowledge and their thinking. Education Policy must make people aware of their Social Evils like dowry, caste system, infanticide, rape, alcoholism, drug addiction, gambling, corruption bribe, prostitute etc. Even though the educational policies have improved, social problems haven't found any solution.

2.OBJECTIVES:

- To determine innovative and creative teaching techniques
- To Understand the Need of self defense education.
- To upgrade the education system

3.LITERATURE REVIEW :

SL. NO.	TITLE	RESEARCHER	YEAR	SUMMARY
1.	TEACHING FOR SOCIAL CHANGE	DILEEP RANJEKAR	2015	In this article he says that it is not merely the teaching of math, social, science or language but how they are taught, keeping in mind the purpose of teaching them and how they are integrated in our day to day life, which would contribute to education and society being better.
2.	EDUTOPIA	BEN JOHNSON	2019	In this article, Creativity and innovation starts with thinking. Imagination and history shows that many things we imagine are later actually created to encourage for creative thinking. Teachers can plan and frame curriculum and provide tools that give students option, voice and choice in order to enable them to be creative.

3.	INDIATODAY		2019	According to the article, Maharashtra government wants to bring self defense as a part of school curriculum in the state. The Maharashtra education minister responded to an online petition fixed by the women self defense coach, Neha from Pune, after hearing many rape cases.
4.	TIMES OF INDIA		2019	In this article, it says that India remains largely unsafe for women. In 2016, 3.38 lakh crimes against women, rape case made up to 11.5% of them. But with only 1 in 4 cases ending up in conviction, it's a painfully slow down to justice for rape victims in the country. This article makes us feel that women should be protected from all kinds of abuses.

4.LIMITATION:

- No importance is given for creative thinking in Government schools
- Compulsion of self defense education is not made in draft educational policy 2019
- Lack of accuracy in case of primary data

5.RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Research is based on secondary data i.e., journals, internet.

6.FINDINGS:

Education has become an object of fear and competition, wherein students and their parents wage war to win a battle to earn money, fame and rank, here no importance is given to creative thinking. The notes, guide books and text are loaded in human gun & shot in exams with an aim to earn the rank. Less conceptual learning by the students but excessively based on memorization.

No proper education is given in government institution. Lesser standard of education is provided in government school when compared to other private schools.

The educational syllabus is outdated not completely but partially. Education is based on traditional form, which focuses on manufacturing our people to become clerk, servant etc but should be focusing on forming practical dreamer, inventor, entrepreneur, and leader rather than Labour and employee. Today's graduates don't take initiatives to start up a business they only employ themselves to work.

The major five countries which are marked as the most dangerous for women by the survey conducted in the year 2017 are India, Afghanistan, Syria, Somalia and Saudi Arabia. New Delhi has the highest number of rape reports among the Indian cities. And it is increasing as the year passes. The rape crime against the women in the year 2016 is 338594, out of which 2167 is gang rape.

7.SUGGESTIONS:

Not everyone can afford for ICSE education system that they offer. The schools must be encouraged to introduce conceptual learning which avoids students to mug up what they are being taught. While this will help students to understand the concepts better, they will also be able to retain and apply them better.

Indian schools and colleges must embrace technology and education with an open heart and propagate the same to the students as it is there, where their future lies. The benefit of technology in the form education is great for both students and teachers. Better training should be given to the graduates before they receive the graduate certificate.

Self defense education should be mandatory in the schools and colleges so that they don't need to look for anyone's help at the time of any unexpected attack on them and can be self-reliant and can also become helpful for others and it can easily adopt the forms and positions of the techniques.

8.CONCLUSION:

Our education system is still having the features what colonial educators inbuilt. Education is not always about earnings in lakh or becoming a big, rich man, it should be about humanism. The education serves as a solution to an ever changing educational landscape by utilizing the knowledge Of students, teachers, families and communities to provide an opportunity to empower & exchange idea, assists people to understand problems & become assets for change.

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